

Questionnaire on impacts brought about by architectural changes at Company A

1. About your experience and roles

1.1 How long have you been working in the technology/engineering field (total time, in years)?

1.2 What is your current position at Company A?

1.3 How long have you been working at Company A (in months or years)?

1.4 What activities do you perform in your daily work?

1.5 What is your level of involvement with frontend development?

Scale: 1 (None) to 5 (High)

1.6 What is your level of involvement with frontend architectural decisions?

Scale: 1 (None) to 5 (High)

2. About development before the architectural changes

2.1 What were the positive points of the old architecture?

2.2 What were the problems faced in the old architecture?

2.3 Among the points mentioned in 2.2, which do you think could be solved by using new technologies?

2.4 Among the points mentioned in 2.2, which do you think could be solved by adopting the new architecture?

3. About the effects brought by the use of new technologies

In this section, we would like to analyze your OBSERVATIONS regarding the effects that the use of new technologies has brought to day-to-day frontend development.

3.1 How do you rate the level of impact brought by the new technologies on the following aspects?

	Don't know	Very negative	Negative	No impact	Positive	Very positive
Project understanding						
Development across multiple teams						
Development speed						
Implementation of new features						
Testability						
Deployment						
Hiring and onboarding						

3.2 Comment on the points you consider relevant about your answers to the previous question.

4. About the effects brought by the new architecture

In addition to the use of new technologies, a new architecture was also implemented. Thus, several changes occurred in the relationship between frontend and backend.

The changes include:

- creation of a gateway;
- extraction of Marketplace functionalities into independent microservices;
- the frontend is now partially served by the Brindle projects;
- each Brindle makes the necessary requests to backend services and assembles the pages appropriately;
- Marketplace continues to serve other pages.

In this section, we would like to analyze your OBSERVATIONS regarding the effects that the new architecture has brought to day-to-day frontend development.

Understand 'new architecture' as all the changes mentioned above.

4.1 How do you rate the level of impact brought by the new architecture on the following aspects?

	Don't know	Very negative	Negative	No impact	Positive	Very positive
Project understanding						
Development across multiple teams						
Development speed						
Implementation of new features						
Testability						
Deployment						
Hiring and onboarding						

4.2 Comment on the points you consider relevant about your answers to the previous question.

Try to explain your answers: why was it very negative? Or what were the positive impacts?

5. About your understanding of the new architecture

5.1 What is a micro frontend to you?

5.2 Based on your knowledge, do you think the new architecture implemented can be considered micro frontends?

5.3 Would the impacts still occur if new technologies were implemented without architectural change? Why?

5.4 Would the impacts still occur if the new architecture were implemented without new technologies? Why?